

Pollen and spikelet sterility of parents, F₁, BC₁, and BC₂ generations at Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan. 1995.

	Plant height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility on bagging (%)
<i>Parent</i>				
IR58025 A	97.1	84	100	100
IR62829 A	85.5	83	100	100
47456	90.1	85	10	13.5
<i>F₁</i>				
IR58025 A/47456	99.1	92	100	100
IR62829 A/47456	92.2	90	100	100
<i>BC₁</i>				
IR58025 A/(47456) ^a	99.3	95	100	100
IR62829 A/(47456)	94.4	90	100	100
<i>BC₂</i>				
IR58025 A/(47456) ^b	99.5	90	100	100
IR62829 A/(47456)	94.6	89	100	100

^a= generation 1. ^b = generation 2.

Comparison of promoters and selectable marker genes for indica rice transformation

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Several selectable marker genes (*nptII*, *hptII*, *dhfr*; *bar*; and *csr1*) have been used for cereal transformation. However, the *bar* gene and, to a lesser degree, the *hpt* gene, have been the most commonly used in recent years. A comparison of the efficacy of these selectable marker genes in indica rice has not been previously reported.

Transient expression of GUS in electroporated protoplasts and bombarded suspension cells. Plasmids with the *gus* gene under the control of promoters pCaMV35S-*gus*, pEmu-*gus*, pRoC-*gus*, and pAct1-*gus* were electroporated into protoplasts. Similarly, pCaMV35S-*gus*, pEmu-*gus*, pAct1-*gus*, and pUbi1-*gus* were used to bombard suspension cells. Except for the RoC promoter, which directs vascular-specific expression, GUS expression was detectable under the control of all promoters tested. Constitutive promoters Act1 and Ubi1 gave the highest expression levels. The order of promoter

strength (from strong to weak) in nonorganized cells of indica rice Chinsurah Boro II was Ubi1 > Act1 > Emu > CaMV35S>RoC. The Ubi1, Act1, and Emu gave 12-, 8-, or 2-fold higher expression levels, respectively, compared with the CamV35S promoter.

Comparison of hpt and bar genes driven by various promoters for stable transformation. Embryogenic calli were cobombarded with pUbi1-*gus* and a range of plasmids containing either the *hph* or *bar* gene controlled by various promoters. Calli staining for GUS activity 1 d after shooting produced more than 300 blue expression units (BEUs) per petri dish of calli bombarded with each plasmid. Although most of the BEUs diminished or disappeared, a few from the pUbi1-*gus*-bombarded calli and any of the three *hph*-containing plasmids gradually increased in size over 2 wk of selection. Four weeks after selection, they formed nodular structures from the surface of the original calli.

Cobombardment of pUbi1-*gus* and pUbi1-*hph* gave the most large BEUs after 4 wk, pEmu-*hph* produced a similar number of smaller BEUs, and pCaMV35S-*hph* gave the fewest and smallest BEUs. Some cultures cobombarded with *gus* and *bar* constructs had modest increase in size and number of BEUs. None of the BEUs developed nodular structures.

Selection of stably transformed cell lines and regeneration of transgenic plants. Embryogenic calli were bombarded with

the *hph* gene constructs (pEmu-*hph* and pUbi1-*hph*) either alone or combined with the *gus* constructs (p40CSD35SAcl-*gus* and pUbi1-*gus*). With the cobombarded calli, about 300-1,500 BEUs were obtained 1 d after shooting.

Without staining for GUS activity, resulting transformed cells or microcalli cannot be identified under the dissecting microscope for at least 1 mo after bombardment. However, staining a few plates of target calli for GUS activity after 2 wk of selection allowed us to observe transformed cell clusters. After three to four subcultures on selection media, fast-growing callus lines could be distinguished among the bombarded calli. These callus lines were individually subcultured onto a new selection medium for further growth.

From 10 experiments and after 2 mo of selection on media, 50 transformed callus lines were obtained from 72 bombarded plates (see table). Of these, 16 regenerated into 79 putative transgenic plants (about 30% regeneration frequency) when placed onto the regeneration medium. Of the six putative transgenic plant lines from cotransformation of *gus* and *hph* genes, two were GUS-positive when the plants were about 5 cm tall. However, GUS activity of one line ceased as the plants matured. All 79 putative transgenic plants (24 sterile and 55 fertile) were transferred to soil in the glasshouse. Most of the sterile plants were derived from experiment 1, which used foundation callus line 1. About 87% of the transgenic plants derived from foundation callus lines 2 and 3 were fertile. Fertile plants were derived from 12 different transformed callus lines (6 from pUbi1-*hph* and 6 from pEmu-*hph*). Southern blot analysis showed that at least one plant from each line contained between one and eight copies of the transgene. Ten of the 12 transgenic plant lines contained both selectable and nonselectable genes, which were introduced on separate plasmids, giving an 83% cointegration frequency.

Calli bombarded with *bar* constructs grew poorly on bialaphos-containing media irrespective of the promoter used to control the *bar* gene. The few BEUs that expanded over time failed to form nodular cell clusters. This suggests the limited use of the *bar* gene in indica rice transformation. Rapid growth of hygromycin-resistant calli

Summary of stable transformation of indica rice cv Chinsurah Boro II.

Experiment	Callus age (mo)/ callus line	Plates bombarded (no.)	<i>hph</i> -resistant callus lines	GUS+ callus lines (no.)	Embryogenic lines (no.)	Plants (no.)	GUS+ plant lines (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	Selectable marker gene	Nonselectable gene
1	8.5/1	8	13	10	3	16	1 (1) ^a	0	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	p40CSD35S- <i>gus</i>
2	9/1	4	5	4	0	-	-	-	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	p40CSD35S- <i>gus</i>
3	7.5/2	3	3	1	2	8	0	7	pUbi1- <i>hph</i>	pUbi1- <i>gus</i>
4	8/2	12	5	2	1	2	0	1	pUbi1- <i>hph</i>	pUbi1- <i>gus</i>
5	7.5/2	7	7	-	3	23	-	22	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV <i>b</i>
6	8/2	7	5	-	1	4	-	4	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
7	8.3/2	8	1	-	1	1	-	1	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
8	8.3/2	9	2	-	1	2	-	1	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
9	5.3/3	7	3	-	3	17	-	13	pUbi1- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
10	5.3/3	7	6	-	1	6	-	6	pUbi1- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
Total		72	50	17	16	79	1	55		

^a Number in parentheses shows transgenic plant line expressing GUS when about 5 cm tall, but not at 20 cm tall. ^b Coding region of rice ragged stunt virus segment 5 driven by various promoters.

and BEU expansion were observed when the *hph* gene was driven by the Ubi 1 promoter, followed by Emu and then CaMV35S. In all three cases, expanding BEUs formed nodular structures indicative of regeneration. The Ubi 1>Emu>CaMV35S ranking

follows the relative levels of GUS expression driven by these promoters in our transient and stable expression studies. From this we infer that stronger promoters enable the most effective selection. The data show that about 2,000-4,000 BEUs 1 d

after shooting are required to achieve each hygromycin-resistant callus line and that such BEUs regenerate into fertile transgenic rice plants with 1-8 copies of the transgene. ■

Transfer of cytoplasmic male sterility in indica rice through protoplast fusion

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Cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) is widely used in hybrid seed production and requires routine transfer of CMS to new genetic backgrounds. Transfer of CMS through conventional breeding requires five to six backcrossings, taking 2-3 yr. However, a one-step transfer of CMS through asymmetric protoplast fusion can be used to shorten this period (Kyoizuka et al 1989).

Plant regeneration, from protoplasts of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines.

Embryogenic calli initiated from the scutella obtained from mature embryos of CMS line V20A were repeatedly subcultured to make them friable. Five hundred 1,000-mg calli were used to initiate cell suspension, which was established after 3-4 mo of regular subculturing at a 4-5 d

interval. Protoplasts, which were isolated, purified, and cultured as described by Bhattacharjee and Gupta (1995), underwent sustained division into microcolonies that became macroscopic after 30-40 d. Protocalli differentiation was obtained 20-30 d after transfer to regeneration medium. Plants were transferred to pots where they flowered and produced sterile pollen grains. Likewise, protocols for protoplasts to plant systems were developed for RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36.

Inactivation of donor and recipient protoplasts and asymmetric fusion.

Because protoplasts of all four lines were dividing on culture, we standardized the dose for their inactivation to undertake asymmetric fusion. Protoplasts of V20A were irradiated with 30 krad gamma ray (Fig. 1a); those of RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36 were inactivated with 10 mM iodoacetamide for 15 min at 20°C (Fig. 1b).

Fusion of gamma ray- and iodoacetamide-inactivated protoplasts of V20A with RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36 was attained with 25 V/1 KHz AC amplitude for 25 s, followed by 900 V DC pulse (2.52 KV/cm field strength) amplitude for 30 µs. Seven 10% fusions were obtained.

Culture of fusion products and plant regeneration, from putative cybrid calli.

Fused protoplasts of V20 A with RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36, along with inactivated protoplasts of V20 A, V20 B, RCPL1-2C, and IR36, were cultured separately. The inactivated protoplasts served as the control. Only fused protoplasts underwent sustained division and formed microcolonies (Fig. 1c), which became macroscopic after 25-30 d of culture. Macrocolonies of putative cybrids between V20A and IR36 differentiated into plantlets when transferred to regeneration medium (Fig. 1d). The plantlets transferred to pots (Fig. 1e) grew to maturity and, as expected, were fertile. Putative cybrid calli between V20 A/RCPL1-2C and V20A/V20 B also differentiated and gave rise to plantlets, which were grown to maturity to check the expression of male sterility. Molecular analyses of mitochondrial DNA of both the sets and parents are in progress.

Cited reference

Bhattacharjee B, Gupta HS. 1995. Fertile plants regenerated from protoplasts of cold-tolerant rice line RCPL1-2C. *J. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 4:61-65. ■